

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE BALLISTIC IMPACT RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE HELMET MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: The response of aramid fibre-reinforced composites to ballistic impact is investigated using the finite element method. A user material routine incorporating fibre breakage, delamination, and matrix crushing has been developed and implemented within the LS-DYNA3D code. Post failure response has been implemented for the various failure modes using the MLT approach. Penetration and backplane delamination due to a 1.1g fragment simulating projectile (FSP) have been predicted for flat plates. The effect of post failure modelling on the extent of damage and on the backplane response is shown to be significant.

KEYWORDS: ballistic impact, post failure, delamination, fibre breakage

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced laminate composite materials offer a variety of desirable characteristics for ballistic helmet applications such as light-weight, high strength, good damage tolerance, and tailorability. However, a major disadvantage of composite materials is the existence of the so-called backplane deformation. This deformation mode occurs through delamination of the composite after partial penetration by the projectile. In such cases, complete penetration of the helmet may be prevented, but the motion of the delaminated backplane can be sufficient to cause serious head injury to the helmet wearer. In order to support further optimisation of the ballistic performance of composite materials, a more thorough understanding of the mechanisms causing backplane deformation is required. This paper presents a numerical study into the parameters determining the extent of backplane deformation.

For a given impact velocity, the extent of penetration and backplane deformation will be determined by the amount of energy transferred from the projectile to the composite material. Langlie and Cheng [1] indicated that punching of the material, fibre breakage, and delamination are the major mechanisms of energy absorption in ballistic composite materials. While a variety of models exist for the prediction of failure initiation in composite materials, recent work [2,3,4] has shown that post failure models can significantly improve damage predictions and reduce mesh sensitivity in models of low velocity transverse impacts on graphite fibre-toughened epoxy resin systems. In the current research, the effects of post

failure behaviour on the predicted delamination and backplane response under ballistic impact conditions are studied.

The impact of a fragment simulating projectile on woven Kevlar laminates is simulated using the LS-DYNA3D [5] finite element code modified to incorporate user material subroutines developed as part of this research. Models of 9 mm thick plates were considered under impact velocities of 500 m/s.

CONSTITUTIVE MODEL

Failure Criteria

Failure criteria for fibre breakage and matrix fracture or crushing were based on a modified version of the Chang and Chang model [6,7] implemented within a user material subroutine written for this work. Delamination was modelled outside of this constitutive routine as described below.

Since the current research considers woven composite materials, the mechanical properties are assumed equal in both in-plane directions. Therefore, fibre breakage can be caused by tensile and shear stresses acting in the in-plane directions, leading to the following failure criteria

$$f_i = \sum_{j=1}^3 \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{S_{ij}} \right)^2 - r_i \geq 0 : \text{failure} \quad (1)$$

$$< 0 : \text{safe}$$

where $i=1,2$, S_{ij} are the in-plane strength values (either tensile or shear), and r_i are the failure thresholds which are equal to 1. When fibre breakage occurs in the i -direction, σ_{ij} are set to zero.

During impact, the composite material in the impacted area will be compressed by the FSP. This will lead to high compressive stresses in the impacted area and high shear stresses in the surrounding area. When these stresses exceed their related strength values, the composite will fail and the FSP will punch a hole in the material. This penetration failure mechanism was modelled using the following criterion

$$f_3 = \sum_{j=1}^3 \left(\frac{\sigma_{3j}}{S_{3j}} \right)^2 - r_3 \geq 0 : \text{failure} \quad (2)$$

$$< 0 : \text{safe}$$

where S_{3j} are the through-thickness strength values (either compressive or shear), and r_3 is the failure threshold and is equal to 1. When penetration failure occurs, all stresses are set to zero.

Post-Failure Model

The post-failure model used in this study, known as the MLT model, was developed by Matzenmiller et al. [8] and is summarised below. This constitutive model was specifically developed to describe anisotropic damage in elastic-brittle fibre-reinforced composites. The elastic-brittle behaviour of these materials is characterised by the formation and evolution of microcracks (surface discontinuities) and cavities (volume discontinuities). These defects are considered irreversible and cause primarily stiffness degradation. A set of damage variables, w_i , were introduced to indicate the state of anisotropic damage and to reduce the stiffness in the damage related directions. The model assumes linear elasticity if the damage state (state of defects) does not change. This implies linear elastic unloading and reloading until the previous damage state is reached again. All non-linear effects of the constitutive behaviour are attributed to damage. Further, the orthotropic nature of the material is maintained throughout the damaging process. The stress-strain response according to the MLT-model, indicating the stiffness reduction due to damage, is depicted in Fig. 1.

Following Matzenmiller, et al. [8], the stiffness reducing damage variables w_i are introduced in the compliance matrix \mathbf{C}

$$[\mathbf{C}] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{(1-w_{11})E_1} & \frac{-\nu_{21}}{E_2} & \frac{-\nu_{31}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{12}}{E_1} & \frac{1}{(1-w_{22})E_2} & \frac{-\nu_{32}}{E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{13}}{E_1} & \frac{-\nu_{23}}{E_2} & \frac{1}{(1-w_{33})E_3} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-w_{12})G_{12}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-w_{23})G_{23}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{(1-w_{13})G_{31}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

and the stiffness matrix is obtained by inverting the compliance matrix: $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{C}^{-1}$

The MLT model is based on classical continuum damage mechanics which assumes that only the undamaged part of the cross-section (net-area) carries loading, i.e. transmits stresses [9]. Consequently, the failure criteria should be defined in terms of the effective stresses, referred to the net area. In the MLT damage model, the effective stresses $\hat{\sigma}$ and the nominal (true) stresses σ are related by

$$\{\hat{\sigma}\} = [\mathbf{M}] \{\sigma\} \quad (4)$$

where,

$$[M] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{1-w_{11}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{1-w_{22}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{1-w_{33}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{1-w_{12}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{1-w_{23}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{1-w_{13}} \end{bmatrix}$$

If we substitute Eqn. 4 into the previously defined failure criteria and write the resulting criteria in terms of strains, we find the following failure criteria for the MLT-model for example for longitudinal tensile fibre failure:

$$g_1 = \left(\frac{c_{11}\varepsilon_{11} + c_{12}\varepsilon_{22} + c_{13}\varepsilon_{33}}{(1-w_{11})S_{11}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{c_{44}\varepsilon_{12}}{(1-w_{12})S_{12}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{c_{66}\varepsilon_{13}}{(1-w_{13})S_{13}} \right)^2 - r_1 \quad (5)$$

The symbol g_i is used to indicate that the failure criteria are expressed in terms of strains instead of stresses. The damage variables are represented by Weibull distribution functions, e.g., for longitudinal tension

$$w_{11} = 1 - e^{-\frac{-1}{m} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{11}}{\varepsilon_{f1}} \right)^m} \quad (8)$$

with,

$$\varepsilon_{f1} = \frac{X_t}{E_1} \quad (9)$$

which is the “nominal” failure strain for a linear elastic material (in the absence of damage growth). Similar relations hold for the other damage parameters. The exponent m in Eqn. 8 determines the shape of the Weibull function. Fig. 2 shows the effect m has on the post-failure strength. High values of m approach instantaneous failure.

The damage thresholds r_i indicate the boundary of the elastic range. The material behaves linear elastically within these boundaries. The role of the damage threshold is equal to that of the yield stress in plasticity. The damage thresholds are initially set to 1, but will monotonically increase with increasing damage once failure has occurred. When at a certain time the strain state exceeds the boundary of the elastic range, the damage thresholds and damage variables need to be updated. Matzenmiller et al. [8] derived a method to accommodate coupling of growth for the individual damage variables in the various damage modes. For reasons of simplicity, damage growth coupling was not implemented in these preliminary calculations and the damage variables only grew when the corresponding strains increased.

The above model was implemented as a user material subroutine for brick elements in LS-DYNA3D. A numerical advantage of the MLT-model is that the damage level and, therefore, the failure mechanism, is based on the strain state. Thus, the duration of unloading after failure directly depends on the strain rate, which is significant in high velocity impacts. The elements that failed in penetration are deleted when w_{33} is equal to 0.999.

Delamination Failure

Delamination is implemented in the current model by meshing the bottom layer of the composite separately and connecting this layer to the rest of the plate with so-called tiebreak

interfaces (slide line type 9 in LS-DYNA3D). The tiebreak interface rigidly connects the nodes of the slave segment to those of the master segment until the failure criterion is exceeded. The tiebreak failure criterion is given by

$$F_{delam} = \left(\frac{\sigma_n}{S_n} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_s}{S_s} \right)^2 \quad (10)$$

where σ_n and σ_s are the normal and shear interface stresses, respectively, and S_n and S_s are the corresponding strengths. Delamination occurs when $F_{delam} > 1$. At this point, the interface is allowed to separate, simulating inter-ply cracking. A similar approach was undertaken by Hung et al. [9], who also modelled delamination in LS-DYNA3D with tiebreak interfaces and their numerical results were in good agreement with experimental data.

MATERIALS

Elastic properties used for the woven aramid material studied are listed in Table 1. The strength values for the composite are given in Table 2. The 4340 steel FSP material was modelled using a yield strength of 1,034 MPa and a hardening modulus of 685 MPa. Young's Modulus was taken as 207 GPa and Poisson's Ratio was 0.3.

Table 1: Elastic properties for woven aramid from [1]

Young's Moduli (MPa)		Poisson's Ratio		Shear Moduli (MPa)		Density (g/cm ²)
E_{11}	E_{33}	ν_{21}	ν_{31}	G_{12}	G_{31}	ρ
28,269	5,516	0.05	0.07	2,579	2,579	1.439

Table 2: Strength properties for woven aramid, partly from [1]

Tensile Strength (MPa)			Compressive Strength (MPa)	Shear Strength (MPa)			
S_{11}	S_{22}	S_n	S_{33}	S_{12}	S_{23}	S_{31}	S_s
482.6	482.6	100.0	350	34.5	350	350	100

The strength values in Table 2 were obtained from [1], except for S_n , S_s , S_{33} , S_{23} , and S_{31} which were chosen to give reasonable results. These values are physically unrealistic, but planned impact tests on plates and helmets will provide more realistic values for these strengths.

MODEL

A finite element model of a woven aramid composite plate was built using I-DEAS Masters Series, Version 2.1. The planar dimensions of the plate were *100 mm* by *100 mm* and the thickness was *9 mm*. The plate was impacted by a .22 calibre chisel-nose Fragment Simulating Projectile (FSP, MIL-P46593). The FSP was made of 4340 steel and weighed *1.1* grams. The impact speed of the FSP was *500 m/s*.

A typical mesh of the flat plate model with the FSP is shown in Fig. 3. Both the plate and the FSP were modelled with 8-node brick elements. To reduce the computational time, only one-half of the problem was modelled through symmetry. Fig. 4 shows a close-up of the impact site and FSP.

An automatic eroding contact algorithm was used to simulate contact and penetration between the FSP and the impacted area of the plate. This algorithm uses a penalty function approach to prevent penetration of contacting elements. In the event of failure of the composite through the erosion criterion given by equation Eqn. 3, the failed elements are deleted and the contact surfaces are automatically updated to consider the next layer of material. A delamination plane (tiebreak interface) was inserted adjacent to the inner-most layer of elements.

RESULTS

Figure 5 compares the effects of post failure modelling on the FSP velocity time histories. In the instantaneous failure model, the stresses are immediately set to zero once the material fails in a certain mode. As already shown in Fig. 2, the stiffness degradation in the MLT model strongly depends on the value of m . Figure 5 shows that a higher amount of post failure strength leads to a higher energy transfer from the FSP to the composite material, which results in greater deceleration of the FSP. When the energy absorption is sufficient, complete penetration of the composite is avoided and backplane deformation occurs. This is the case for $m=2$, where the FSP is completely stopped by the backplane and rebounds. In all other cases the backplane is completely penetrated by the FSP. The predicted final velocity of the FSP after complete penetration depends heavily upon the post failure treatment. Figure 5 also shows that the MLT predictions approach those using instantaneous failure for high values of m .

The backplane displacement time histories for a node located at the centre of the delaminating backplane are shown Fig. 6 as function of the post failure exponent m . The only case for which the backplane was not penetrated by the FSP was for $m=2$. In all other post failure cases the backplane was initially pushed down by the FSP, but eventually failed in crushing. Therefore, the nodal displacements for these cases are not representative for the total backplane displacement. The instantaneous failure case was omitted because the backplane area under the FSP was completely eroded.

Figure 7 shows a series of deformed mesh plots for $m=2$. Penetration of the upper layers occurs through crushing and transverse shear failure as seen in Figs 7 (a) and (b). The nature of the eroding contact algorithm can be observed as a progressive removal of elements ahead of the penetrator. As the FSP nears the backplane its velocity decreases, resulting in lower normal compressive strain rates and through-thickness shear strain rates. This enables the in-plane stresses to build up before the element is eroded. Therefore, the dominant failure mode will gradually change from crushing to fibre breakage. When the FSP reaches the backplane its velocity will be so low that crushing of the underlying composite material will no longer occur and the composite will fail in fibre breakage and delamination. This agrees with Langlie and Cheng's findings [1], who observed that the failure process in a composite plate under ballistic impact can be visualised by three subsequent layers dominated by through-thickness failure, in-plane tensile failure, and delamination failure, respectively. Figure 8 shows the case for $m=10$, where the backplane is initially pushed down, but eventually fails in crushing.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The foregoing shows that the damage exponent m has a considerable effect on the impact response of the composite material. Unfortunately, m has no physical meaning and cannot be directly determined from experiments. Williams and Vaziri [4] suggested that m can be numerically calibrated to give the best representation for a certain impact test. Impact tests on flat plates and helmets are underway and these tests will hopefully yield a reasonable estimate for m . In addition to m , the numerical damage predictions are also strongly affected by the strength values. Material testing on the woven composite material and the aforementioned impact tests will yield better estimates for these strength parameters.

Despite its limitations, the implemented post failure model yields more realistic results than could have been obtained with the instantaneous failure models currently implemented in LS-DYNA3D. The MLT model is a promising and versatile numerical tool for simulating progressive damage in fibre reinforced composite materials.

In future, mesh refinement and delamination layers between each ply layer or between groups of plies at regular intervals through thickness will further improve the current model. Post failure modelling in the delamination criterion and linking the constitutive model with the tie-break interface model will also yield a more realistic response.

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Fig. 1: Stress-strain relation for MLT-model

Fig. 2: Effect of failure exponent m on post-failure strength

Fig. 3: Flat plate model

Fig. 4: Close-up of impact area

Fig. 5: FSP velocity time history as function of post-failure treatment

Fig. 6: Backplane displacement history as function of post-failure treatment

Fig. 7: Sequence of penetration of plate by projectile and delamination of backplane

Fig. 8: Complete penetration of plate at $t=60\mu$ s ($m=10$)